
YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM EDUCATION YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM EDUCATION

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Annotation.

the article is devoted to the study of the main power of our Motherland, the process of upbringing of our youth in the spirit of military patriotism, which is the main pillar of our development, and the main priorities in the upbringing of military patriotism. At the same time, we will also introduce young people to the system of military patriotic education, as well as some attitudes that are hindered in the education of military patriotism today

Keywords.

Homeland, Patriot, military, concept, veteran, servant, hand-to-hand combat, summer biathlon, sniper

Introduction

Educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotism is a multi - stage, systematic, purposeful and coordinated activity of state bodies, public associations and organizations, aimed at forming a sense of loyalty to the motherland in young people, raising them as individuals capable of fulfilling their civil duty and constitutional obligations, protecting the interests of society and the state. The main goal aimed at educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotism is to show activity in young people in various branches of society, especially in types of civil service associated with the military sphere, to be devoted to constitutional and military duty in a peaceful and military environment, to form in them such important characteristics as high responsibility and responsibility for the fate of When educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism, the following are defined as the main tasks:

- to educate young people in the spirit of national ideology and loyalty to the Republic of Uzbekistan, its people and its president, deeply instill in their heart and mind that the protection of the Motherland is an honorable and sacred duty;

- to be proud of our ancient history and culture, our national heroes who selflessly fought for the independence and prosperity of our native land, to form a

feeling of being worthy of them, to strengthen confidence in the power and potential of our national army;

-the need for physically strong and spiritually mature youth for our national army, the understanding that military service is a sacred duty for every citizen of Uzbekistan, as well as strengthening theoretical and practical skills in this regard;

- formation of skills in young people to approach the political and social processes taking place around us and in the world based on our national interests, ideological immunity to various internal and external threats;

- to educate young people with the skills of adaptation to combat actions, quick and independent decision-making in any complex situations, effective use of modern military equipment; to stand ready to defend the interests of Uzbekistan not only in the military sphere, but in all aspects of life, at every step, to be selfless for the country-to instill in the minds of young people

Raising young people in the spirit of military patriotism is a growing age

it is said that the multi-stage, systematic, purposeful and coordinated activities of state bodies, public associations and organizations aimed at forming the loyalty of the generation to the motherland, regardless of nationality, language, profession and social origin, educating them as individuals capable of fulfilling civil duties and constitutional obligations, protecting the interests of society and our state. The main role in the education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism is played by the activities of educational institutions. The reason is that the main time of youth education at the educational institution, which is aimed at obtaining education, is given in preschool education, general secondary schools, secondary specialized, vocational education and higher education institutions.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

A number of works are also being carried out in our country to educate young people in the spirit of military patriotism. The reason is that the education of young people in the face of military patriotism is one of the priorities of state policy. In the current complex era of globalization, information communication technologies in rapidly developing conditions determine the urgent tasks and ways of solving them related to the education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism, the role and importance of state and non-profit organizations, family, neighborhood, educational institutions in this regard, their interaction taking into account national and international legal norms. According to the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 140 of February 23, 2018,

the" concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism " was developed, in Chapter 2 of this concept, the purpose and main

the tasks are clearly defined. The purpose of educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotism is to show activity in young people in various branches of society, especially in types of civil service associated with the military sphere, to be loyal to the Constitution and military duty in a peaceful and military environment, to form in them such important characteristics as high responsibility and responsibility for the fate of Results

The following is an overview of the military-patriotic education of young people the main functions are:

- to educate young people in the spirit of national idea and devotion to the motherland, their deep into the heart and mind that the protection of the Motherland is an honorable and sacred duty impregnation;

- our ancient history and culture, our native land national who selflessly fought for independence and prosperity the feeling of being proud of our heroes, worthy of them formation, strengthening confidence in the power and potential of our national army;

- physically energetic and spiritually mature youth to our national army strengthening the understanding that military service is a sacred duty for every citizen of Uzbekistan, as well as theoretical and practical skills in this regard;

- political-social, which is happening around us and in the world in young people approach processes based on our national interests ideological against Skills, various internal and external threats formation of immunity;

- to educate young people with the skills of quick and independent decision-making in any complex situations, effective use of modern military equipment;

- To be prepared to protect the interests of Uzbekistan not only in the military sphere, but also in all aspects of life, to be selfless for the country

- to instill in the minds of young people through life examples and impressive means that this is the requirement of today.

Education of mercenaries in the spirit of military patriotism is told about the multi-stage, systematic, purposeful and coordinated activities of state bodies, public associations and organizations, aimed at forming loyalty to the motherland, fulfilling civil duties and constitutional obligations, as individuals capable of protecting the interests of society and our state, regardless of nationality, language, profession and social origin of the growing younger generation. The main role in the education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism is played by the

activities of educational institutions. The reason is that the main time of youth education at the educational institution, which is aimed at obtaining education, is given in preschool education, general secondary schools, secondary specialized, vocational education and higher education institutions.

A number of works are also being carried out in our country to educate young people in the spirit of military patriotism. The reason is that the education of young people in the face of military patriotism is one of the priorities of state policy. In the current complex era of globalization, information communication technologies in rapidly developing conditions determine the urgent tasks related to the education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism and ways of their resolution, the role and importance of state and non-profit organizations, family, neighborhood, educational institutions in this regard, their interaction taking into account national and international legal norms. According to the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 140 of February 23, 2018, the “concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism” was developed, the 2 chapters of this concept clearly define the purpose and main tasks of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism. The purpose of educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotism is to show activity in young people in various branches of society, especially in types of civil service associated with the military sphere, to be loyal to the Constitution and military duty in a peaceful and military environment, to form in them such important characteristics as high responsibility and responsibility for the fate of

The following are the main tasks of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism:

- to educate young people in the spirit of national idea and devotion to the motherland, to deeply instill in their heart and mind the glorious and holy duty of protection of the motherland;

- to be proud of our ancient history and culture, our national heroes who selflessly fought for the independence and prosperity of our native land, to form a feeling of being worthy of them, to strengthen confidence in the power and potential of our national army;

- strengthening the understanding of the need for physically strong and spiritually mature youth for our national army, the holy duty of military service for every citizen of Uzbekistan, as well as theoretical and practical skills in this regard;

- formation of skills in young people to approach the political and social processes taking place around us and in the world based on our national interests, ideological immunity to various internal and external threats;

- to educate young people to the qualification of quick and independent decision-making, effective use of modern military equipment in any complex situations;

- To be prepared to protect the interests of Uzbekistan not only in the military sphere, but also in all aspects of life, to be selfless for the country

- this is the demand of today to instill Yekani in the minds of young people through life examples and impressive means.

I believe that it is advisable to carry out the tasks set by the "concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism " on the education of students of a higher educational institution in the spirit of military patriotism:

First of all, the systematic organization of training on topics related to the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the military profession and the life of the military in the "hours of spirituality" in order to promote the essence of the reforms carried out in the field of Armed Forces in our country and to further strengthen respect for the military profession among students;

Secondly, on January 14, on the occasion of the "day of the citizens of the Fatherland", military personnel and veterans of the Armed Forces who succumb to rich life experience, have won various competitions and competitions in the fields of science, culture and sports, organized scheduled meetings with students with the participation of servicemen and participants of war, participants of other, Organization of military sports competitions between servicemen and student youth serving in the military on a term and contract basis, selection of essays on topics related to the military sphere, Organization of spiritual and educational activities;

Thirdly, on the occasion of the "day of Remembrance and appreciation " may 9, Veterans of World War II and frontline labor, military personnel killed in the performance of duty of service during the years of independence and law enforcement officers, organize the holding of cultural and educational and patriotic events to explain, promote and promote the importance of courage and courage among student youth, welcome, Organization of a visit of student youth with the participation of leaders to their place of residence in order to receive a message from Holi;

Fourth the organization of military sports clubs in educational institutions, including the opening of clubs from sports such as “hand-to-hand combat”, “summer biathlon”, “Sniper” and ensuring the participation of student youth;

Fifth organization of cooperation with military units of the Ministry of Defense Of The Republic of Uzbekistan, close to the educational institution, development and implementation of a cooperation plan for patriotic education;

Spiritual and educational held at the educational institution of the sixth exchange of experience in ensuring the participation of military personnel of the armed forces in events and organizing spiritual and educational activities with military personnel.

DISCUSSION

In”the concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism institution of Higher Education based on the established tasks in order to educate his students in the spirit of military patriotism I think it is advisable to carry out the tasks: Firstly implemented in the field of Armed Forces in the country systematic organization of training on topics related to the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the military profession and the life of the military in the “hours of morale”in order to promote the essence of the reforms being carried out and to further strengthen respect and attention to the military profession among students; Secondly, on January 14, on the occasion of the “day of the citizens of the Fatherland”, military personnel and veterans of the Armed Forces with rich life experience, military personnel who have won various competitions and competitions in the fields of science, culture and sports, participants of war, scheduled meetings with student youth with the participation of other participants in combat military serving on a term and contract basis military sports competitions between servicemen and student youth organizing, a selection of essays on topics related to the military sphere, Organization of spiritual and educational activities; thirdly, on the occasion of the “day of Remembrance and appreciation” of May 9, Veterans of World War II and frontline labor, military personnel and law enforcement killed during the performance of duty of service during the years of independence of the perseverance, courage and courage shown by the employees of the making bodies organize the holding of cultural and educational and patriotic activities to explain, promote and promote the importance among student youth, greet these categories of persons, organize a visit of student youth to their place of residence with the participation of leaders in order to receive a message from the state;

Fourth the organization of military sports clubs in educational institutions, including the opening of clubs from sports such as “hand-to-hand combat”, “summer biathlon”, “Sniper” and ensuring the participation of student youth; Fifth organization of cooperation with military units of the Ministry of Defense Of The Republic of Uzbekistan, close to the educational institution, development and implementation of a cooperation plan for patriotic education;

Spiritual and educational held at the educational institution of the sixth participation of military personnel of the Armed Forces in events exchange of experience in the provision and organization of spiritual and educational activities with military personnel. Today, in the construction of a democratic legal state in our country and the establishment of a free civil society, the upbringing of the younger generation based on the rich historical, spiritual and cultural heritage created by our great ancestors is among the urgent tasks. That is why the need to restore the historical, spiritual and cultural heritage of our people from the first days of independence of our state and make good use of it in the spiritual renewal of society has become an issue raised to the level of Public Policy. It is known that the progress of each nation cannot be imagined without its history, spiritual values and cultural heritage. High spirituality is an invincible force, and a state and nation with such power cannot be overcome. Our country has rich historical roots in the issue of historical, spiritual and cultural heritage. Our ancestors made a worthy contribution to the scourge of civilization in the matter of culture and spirituality. Its expression can be seen in our historical heritage, where “Avesto” has made a significant contribution to world civilization and political spirituality. Also, the Timur tuzuks, the boburnoma, the hadiths of Bukhari are a large historical, spiritual and cultural heritage. During the years of independence, the historical, spiritual and cultural heritage of our people restored their destiny, and the noble efforts to bring decoration to the descendants, so how many names of our allomas were restored, historical monuments were repaired, shrines of our great ones were landscaped. Thousands of pilgrims were restored to themselves as historical, spiritual and cultural heritage of the people. In carrying out these good deeds, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. It is appropriate to highlight the efforts and role of Mirziyoyev. As evidence of our opinion, the great alloma on the Land of Kashkadarya, a major representative of the moturidia doctrine, the author of about 15 books on the issue of purity of Islamic faith Abu Muin Nasafi, the great Hadith scholar alloma Abu Isa Muhammad at-Termizi in the District of Sherabad, the great Bahauddin Naqshband Hazrat in Bukhara, the mosque named after Imam

Termizi in Tashkent and the mausoleum of Suzuk ota, Also, as a clear example of our country's care to preserve the historical, spiritual and cultural heritage of the people of Uzbekistan, decree PF-4956 of February 15, 2017 "on measures to further improve the management system in the field of Culture and sports", resolution PQ-2995 of May 24, 2017" measures to further improve the system of preservation, research and promotion of ancient written, Resolution PQ-3074 of June 20, 2017 "on the establishment of the Center for research on foreign cultural property of Uzbekistan under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan", resolution PQ-3105 "on the organization of the activities of the public council on the newest history of Uzbekistan under the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated June 30, 2017 " on the restoration of ancient history and rich culture of our people, , it is important to organize such works as the improvement of the Holy steps, the preservation of manuscripts of research institutions, on the basis of which our compatriots, first of all, educate our young generation in the spirit of respect for the great spiritual heritage of our people, kindness and devotion to our native land, identify cultural assets held abroad, about the history and culture of In addition, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. On the direct initiative and commission of Mirziyoyev, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted" on the establishment of a memorial complex named after the outstanding enlightener Ishakkhan Ibrat in the Turakurgan District of Namangan region", dated April 14, 2017" on additional measures for the further development and improvement of the activities of the Khorezm Ma'mun Academy "No. 211, dated June 15, 2017" on the construction of objects of, decisions" on measures to improve the regulation and control of the organization of work in the field of reconstruction and perfect repair " No. 376 are regulatory documents of particular importance in the organization of protection and effective use of objects of cultural heritage. It is advisable to educate our youth in the spirit of patriotism, loyalty to the motherland and instill in their minds the value of our spiritual assets, first of all, to reveal the meaning of the concepts of historical, spiritual and cultural heritage, to explain their role and role in the development of the civilization of the human society. In particular, spiritual heritage-spiritual wealth that has reached us from our ancestors, ancestors-is a complex of political, philosophical, legal and religious views, norms of morality, achievements in science, historical, artistic and artistic works. So far, there are 74 objects on the National List of intangible cultural heritage of Uzbekistan. As a unique example of universal heritage, four ancient cities on the territory of Uzbekistan - Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Shahrisabz-are

included in the UNESCO World Cultural Heritage List, Navruz holiday, great song, traditions related to "Shashmaqom", Askiya, Uzbek pilaf are included in the list of "World Memory" rare manuscripts collected at the center of Oriental manuscripts named after Abu Rayhon Beruniy under the Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies. More than 100,000 manuscript works are now held in the book funds of Uzbekistan. Manuscripts of medieval Oriental allomas and thinkers today form the "Golden fund" of libraries in Europe and Asia, Great Britain, Germany, Spain, Russia, France, Egypt, India, Iran and many other countries. The importance of archaeological monuments located on the territory of our country is invaluable when it comes to historical heritage. Uzbekistan occupies one of the leading places in the world in terms of the number of archaeological monuments. More than 7.5 thousand objects of material cultural heritage, of which 4,308 objects of archeology, 2,079 objects of architecture, 694 objects of art, 395 landmarks[8] have been preserved, taken into state protection. Objects of cultural heritage are divided into objects of material and intangible cultural heritage according to Article 3 of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the protection and use of objects of cultural heritage". Objects of material cultural heritage in turn will consist of ensembles, attractions and monuments of historical, scientific, artistic or exceptional cultural value

Conclusion

Education in the education of young people in the spirit of military-patriotism the role of its institutions is extremely large, and educational work is carried out together with education in an educational institution. The spiritual and educational activities of students of higher educational institutions in the educational institution in the spirit of military patriotism are carried out through activities organized in cooperation with military personnel.

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